

Livelihood Strategies and Crop Production Status of Charlands Dwellers in Bangladesh

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Abstract

The study was carried out in Charlands of Bangladesh to evaluate the livelihood strategies and crop production status of Charlands dwellers. Total 150 beneficiaries were selected randomly as sample of the study. Socioeconomic data were collected during May to June 2019 using a predetermined interview schedule. People in Charlands of Bangladesh mainly live at the mercy of limited social services, poor income, insecure shelter and illiteracy. Cropping intensity of the Charlands was found very low (145 to 162%) due to limited cultivability of land for long time inundation. Rice, maize, jute, vegetable were the major crops cultivated in the Charlands based on the area coverage. Crop production is less due to unfertile Charlands. Majority of the Charland farmers possessed moderate knowledge on crop management practice having favorable attitude towards the same. Soil management practices were mainly performed using chemical fertilizers ignoring use of organic manures.

Keywords: Charlands, livelihood, crop, soil management, organic manures

Introduction

Charlands is a Bengali term, which means Riverine Island in English. Charlands is a formed area of land because of gradual built up of transported constituent components of water bodies; especially soils and other solid minerals. According to Banglapedia (2014) the Charlands is a tract of land surrounded by the waters of an ocean, sea, lake, or stream; any accretion in a river course or estuary. The charlands consists of all types of bars including both lateral (point-bars) and medial (braid-bars). Traditionally and predominantly, Bangladesh is agriculture based country and about 75.7 percent of population is engaged in agriculture for their livelihood (BBS, 2012). According to Rahman and Reza (2011) most of these sandbars stay unused and barren because of their unfertile sandy characteristics. Noman *et al.* (2014) reported that in Bangladesh agriculture; sandbar cropping is an innovative practice, which was first introduced in Gaibandha district by some farmers in 2005. Since 2009, a NGO named Practical Action Bangladesh (PAB) has been introducing sandbar cropping technology suitable for use in unfertile sandbars and supporting extreme poor to cultivate pumpkins. The Charlands of Bangladesh are divided into five sub regions such as the Jamuna, the Ganges, the Padma, the upper Meghna and the lower Meghna river. The old Brahmaputra and Tista similarly constitute some Charlands areas. A Charlands is a strip of land otherwise a bar which has developed from the river-bed following deposition and accretion of silt and alluvium. Also the Charlands can be of two types: attached and island. An island Charlands is the land which even in the dry season, can only be reached from the mainland crossing a main river channel. But the attached Charlands are accessible from the mainland without crossing a channel during the dry season (Sarker *et al.*, 2007). EGIS 2000 found that on an average 5% of Bangladeshi population as well as 6.5 million people live on the Charlands covering almost 5% of the total land area of the country. Kelly and Chowdhury (2002) reported that the riverine sand and silt landmasses known as Charlands in Bengali are home to over 5 million people in Bangladesh. The whole of the Charlands is unstable and prone to annual flooding. Roy *et al.* (2007) reported that the char dwellers are some of the poorest and most vulnerable people particularly those who live on the island or attached river Charlands. Floods are the main natural hazard faced by char dwellers and, in recent

years, there were severe floods in 1987, 1988, and 1998 and more recently in 2004 and 2007. In 1987 and 1988, less than 10% of the char area was above water during peak flood. By comparison, in the 'high normal flood' of 1991, about 50% of char land was flooded. Over 90% of houses were flooded in 1988 compared to about one third of the houses in 1991. Normal monsoon floods in the Charlands tend to be last for weeks rather than months, but floods can occur several times during the monsoon season (Tod, 2007).

Shahiduzzaman *et al.* (2013) found that nearly half of the landless Charlands people were food insecure. The char dwellers are facing with the problem of poverty which demonstrates itself in landlessness, joblessness, illiteracy, malnutrition and vulnerability to regular natural disasters. Besides this, the stability of chars in wandering rivers could be explained by the fact that in such rivers attached Charlands develop out of island Charlands, which results in a continuity in the process of Charlands formation. This is absent in a braided river like Jamuna, where the attached and island Charlands are formed more randomly and independently (Sarker *et al.*, 2003). The dynamics of river is also different between Padma and Jamuna. The floodplains beside the right bank of the Jamuna River are older than those of the left bank. The floodplains beside the left bank of the Padma and lower Meghna rivers are older than those of the right bank, and the length-averaged bank erosion rate was found to be much higher of the left bank (ISPAN, 1995). The present study tries to find out the livelihood strategies and crop production status of Charlands dwellers in Bangladesh.

Materials and methods

According to Urdong (1968) research methodology is the underlying principles and rules of organization of philosophical system or inquiry procedure. A project implemented in the Char Shaluka of Sariakandi upazila in Bogura district, Naobhangar Char of Jamalpur Sadar upazila in Jamalpur district and Maijbari Char of Kazipur upazila in Sirajgonj district to evaluate the livelihood strategies and crop production status of Charlands dwellers in Bangladesh. In order to collect relevant information from the participants, an instrument was carefully designed keeping the objectives of the study in mind. The instrument contained equally open and closed questions. Pre-testing of interview schedule was conducted with ten farmers. The final version of the instrument was prepared based on pre-test and the suggestions and comments of the panel of experts.

The socio-demographic information of the Charlands dwellers included their educational level, house type, toilet type, source of water, access to electricity and access to medical care, farm size, farming experience, contact with information sources, annual income (BDT), knowledge on crop management practices, attitude towards crop management practices. The crop production information in different Charlands considered for this study were crops cultivated, cropping intensity, soil management practices. Necessary coding of data was done after collecting the data and transferred this into computer for analysis. After collection of data, all the information contained in the interview schedule was modified before leaving a respondent. Collected data were analyzed based on the objectives of the study. Simple statistics like range, mean, percent, standard deviation etc. were counted to express results.

Results and discussion

Socio-demographic information

The sampled inhabitants were predominantly illiterate, living in a poor housing condition with low hygienic condition (Table 1-3). Their water source was mostly from personally owned shallow tubewell and only a few had connection to solar/national grid for electricity (Table 4-5). On a positive note, they accessed medical care from medical doctors (MBBS) whom they normally visit at their respective upazila sadar (Table 6).

Table 1. Educational level of char dwellers

Categories	Char Shaluka		Naobhangar Char		Maijbari Char	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Illiterate	30	60.0	45	90	36	72.0
Primary school	12	24.0	4	8.0	7	14.0
Secondary school	5	10.0	1	2.0	2	4.0

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High school	2	4.0	0	0.0	4	8.0
BS degree	1	2.0	0	0.0	1	2.0
Total	50	100.0	50	100.0	50	100.0

Table 2. House type of char dwellers

Categories	Char Shaluka		Naobhangar Char		Maijbari Char	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Thatch	1	2.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Tin roofed	7	14.0	0	0.0	16	32.0
Tin	41	82.0	50.0	100.0	34	68.0
Bricks and cement	1	2.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Total	50	100.0	50	100.0	50	100.0

Table 3. Toilet type of char dwellers

Categories	Char Shaluka		Naobhangar Char		Maijbari Char	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Sanitary latrine	6	12.0	0	0.0	6	12.0
Semi-sanitary latrine	34	68.0	5	10.0	42	84.0
Open space/bushes	10	20.0	45	90.0	2	4.0
Total	50	100.0	50	100.0	50	100.0

Table 4. Source of water of char dwellers

Categories	Char Shaluka		Naobhangar Char		Maijbari Char	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Self-owned	40	80.0	50.0	100.0	43	86.0
Communal	9	18.0	0	0.0	6	12.0
Government	1	2.0	0	0.0	1	2.0
Total	50	100.0	50	100.0	50	100.0

Table 5. Access to electricity of char dwellers

Categories	Char Shaluka		Naobhangar Char		Maijbari Char	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Solar/National grid	34	68.0	45	90.0	40	80.0
No access	16	32.0	5	10.0	10	20.0
Total	50	100.0	50	100.0	50	100.0

Table 6. Medical care of char dwellers

Categories	Char Shaluka		Naobhangar Char		Maijbari Char	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Kobiraj	1	2.0	5	10.0	0	0.0
Village quack	4	8.0	0	0.0	5	10.0
Medical doctor (MBBS)	37	74.0	40	80.0	45	90.0
Consultant	8	16.0	5	10.0	0	0.0
Total	50	100.0	50	100.0	50	100.0

In short, people in the selected Charlands live at the mercy of limited social services, poor shelter and illiteracy.

Farming information

Added to the low socio-demographic profile, the respondents' household were found largely earning less than one hundred and fifty thousand Taka per annum. On average, their contact with information sources was very low where they hardly got engaged with extension worker (Table 9). Despite being farming their major livelihood from which they acquired high experience they could not expand their production due to

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small land holdings (mostly less than a hectare) couple with inadequate knowledge on crop management practices, especially soil amendments that helps improve soil health for high productivity (Table 7-8, 11).

Table 7. Farm size of char dwellers

Categories	Char Shaluka		Mean	Naobhangar Char		Mean	Maijbari Char		Mean
	No.	%		No.	%		No.	%	
Landless (up to 0.02 ha)	3	6.0		2	4.0		4	8.0	
Marginal (0.021-0.2 ha)	10	20.0		12	24.0		13	26.0	
Small (0.2- 1.0 ha)	25	50.0		26	52.0		18	36.0	
Medium (1.01 – 3.0 ha)	7	14.0	0.53	5	10.0	0.48	14	28.0	0.65
Large (> 3.0 ha)	5	10.0		5	10.0		1	2.0	
Total	50	100.0		50	100.0		50	100.0	

Table 8. Farming experience of char dwellers

Categories	Char Shaluka		Mean	Naobhangar Char		Mean	Maijbari Char		Mean
	No.	%		No.	%		No.	%	
Low (up to 20)	19	38.0		8	16.0		25	50.0	
Medium (21 – 40)	22	44.0		17	34.0		21	42.0	
High (> 40)	9	18.0	28.44	25	50.0	29.50	4	8.0	21.70
Total	50	100.0		50	100.0		50	100.0	

Table 9. Contact with information sources of char dwellers

Categories	Char Shaluka		Mean	Naobhangar Char		Mean	Maijbari Char		Mean
	No.	%		No.	%		No.	%	
Very low (up to 5)	33	66.0		30	60.0		50	100.0	
Low (6 – 10)	17	34.0	4.64	20	40.0	4.84	0	0.0	2.28
Total	50	100.0		50	100.0		50	100.0	

Table 10. Annual income of char dwellers

Categories	Char Shaluka		Mean	Naobhangar Char		Mean	Maijbari Char		Mean
	No.	%		No.	%		No.	%	
Low (up to 150,000)	32	64.0		22	44.0		41	82.0	
Medium (151,000 – 300,000)	11	22.0		8	16.0		7	14.0	
High (> 300,000)	7	14.0	181,164	20	40.0	190,253	2	4.0	114,070
Total	50	100.0		50	100.0		50	100.0	

Table 11. Knowledge of char dwellers on crop management practices (Out of total scores 30.0)

Categories	Char Shaluka		Mean	Naobhangar Char		Mean	Maijbari Char		Mean
	No.	%		No.	%		No.	%	
Low (up to 10)	8	16.0		10	20.0		7	14.0	
Moderate (11 - 20)	41	82.0		25	50.0		43	86.0	
High (> 20)	1	2.0	13.75	15	30.0	11.20	0	0.0	12.89
Total	50	100.0		50	100.0		50	100.0	

Attitude of the respondent Charlands dwellers towards crop management practices, soil in particular was expressed favorably, perhaps, due to a conviction that good management leads high yield (Table 12).

Table 12. Attitude of char dwellers on crop management practices (Out of total scores 30.0)

Categories	Char Shaluka		Mean	Naobhangar Char		Mean	Maijbari Char		Mean
	No.	%		No.	%		No.	%	
Unfavorable (up to 15)	3	6.0		5	10.0		3	6.0	
Favorable (16 - 30)	47	94.0		45	90.0		47	94.0	

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Highly favorable (> 30)	0	0.0	21.90	0	0.0	17.13	0.0	0.0	19.76
Total	50	100.0		50	100.0		50	100.0	

Crops, cropping intensity and soil management information

Ten crops were found under cultivation in Char Shaluka out of which jute and rice were dominant in terms of mean area coverage (34.26%). From Naobhangar Char, 11 crops were cultivated with vegetable and rice covering (67.0%) a large mean space. In Maijbari Char, nine crops were under cultivation with maize, jute, and rice having large mean coverage (84.62%) (Table 13). The cropping intensity was low across the Charlands (Table 14).

Table 13. Coverage of Charlands with different crops

Crops cultivated Categories	Char Shaluka	Naobhangar Char	Maijbari Char
	Mean area coverage (%)	Mean area coverage (%)	Mean area coverage (%)
Rice	34.26	30.00	23.64
Wheat	3.00	2.00	0.40
Maize	2.36	7.00	32.60
Millet	0.06	1.00	0.60
Mustard	0.00	2.00	0.84
Chili	13.30	5.00	8.50
Groundnut	2.50	5.00	4.84
Potato	0.50	2.00	0.00
Sweet potato	0.54	1.00	0.00
Vegetables	7.64	35.00	0.20
Jute	35.84	10.00	28.38

Table 14. Cropping intensity in Charlands

Types of Cropping	Char Shaluka	Naobhangar Char	Maijbari Char
	Mean coverage (%)	Mean coverage (%)	Mean coverage (%)
Single cropping	10.30	40.00	18.50
Double cropping	37.40	35.00	69.10
Triple cropping	38.60	15.00	9.20
Fallow	14.50	10.00	3.20
Cropping intensity	162	145	155

Soil management practices in all the Charlands were mainly done using chemical fertilizers with more than 90.0 percent coverage in both Naobhangar Char and Maijbari Char. Nonetheless, a negligible few did use organic practices such as incorporation of crop residue, cow dung, and manure (19.2%) (Table 15). In essence, the pilot evidence has established a state of disadvantage in the chosen Charlands in terms of status of life, main livelihood source (farming) and unsustainable soil management practices.

Table 15. Coverage of different soil management practices in Charlands

Soil management practices	Char Shaluka	Naobhangar Char	Maijbari Char
	Mean coverage (%)	Mean coverage (%)	Mean coverage (%)
Chemical fertilizer	77.00	90.00	92.20
Crop residue incorporation	0.30	0.00	0.00
Vermicompost	0.10	0.00	0.80
Cow dung	12.10	5.00	6.20
Household waste	0.00	0.00	0.00
Standard organic fertilizer	0.00	0.00	0.00
Quick compost	0.00	0.00	0.00
Poultry manure	0.00	0.00	0.00
Green manure	0.50	0.00	0.80
Biochar	0.10	0.00	0.00
Ash	6.50	4.00	0.00
Mulching	3.24	1.00	0.00

Conclusion

Results obtained from baseline survey indicate that the inhabitants were predominantly illiterate, living in a poor housing condition with low hygienic condition using water from personally owned shallow tube well and they had no connection to the national grid, though a good percent had access solar connection. Their contact with information sources was reported very low where they hardly got engaged with extension worker. Despite being farming their major livelihood from which they acquired high experience they could not expand their production due to small land holdings couple with inadequate knowledge on crop management practices, especially soil amendments that helps improve soil health for high productivity. Ten crops were found under cultivation in Char Shaluka out of which jute and rice were dominant in terms of mean coverage (34.26%). From Naobhangar Char, 11 crops were cultivated with vegetable and rice covering (67.0%) a large mean space. In Maijbari Char, nine crops were under cultivation with maize, jute, and rice having large mean coverage (84.62%). The cropping intensity was low across the Charlands. In terms of cropping intensity, it was found alternated between cereals, vegetables, fiber, and fallow. Soil management practices in all the Charlands were mainly done using chemicals with more than ninety percent coverage in both Naobhangar Char and Maijbari Char. Nonetheless, a negligible few did use organic practices such as incorporation of crop residue, cow dung and manure.

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